

Dynamic Functional Split Orchestration

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ABSTRACT

With the envisioned requirements for future mobile networks and the adoption of Software Defined Networks, finer control over the resources that enable a full dynamic Radio Access Network has become paramount. This work proposes a solution to control the Processing Units within an Open Virtual Radio Access Network. The solution presented seeks to integrate the Optical and Functional Split control with the O-RAN alliance architecture. The management of the Functional Split will further optimise transport and computing resources responding to the requirements of ever-dynamic scenarios.

Keywords: Dynamic Functional Split, Network Orchestration, Slicing.

1. ORCHESTRATING DYNAMIC FUNCTIONAL SPLIT IN VRAN

The shift towards Virtual Radio Access Networks (VRANs) targets the rapid repair, fast software development cycles for the deployment of new features and the possibility of using off-the-shelf components for necessary processing. Within this paradigm, the emergence of Open Radio Access Networks (O-RANs), based on Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) with standardized interfaces coupled with the intelligent control of said functions, has enabled the deployment of Next Generation Networks with improved flexibility. The solution presented in this work considers general-purpose computing nodes capable of inter-working with purpose-built counterparts, extending market forecasts detailing the intent of deploying RANs with multiple processing nodes [1].

Figure 1: VRAN logical architecture composed of O-RAN alliance components Service Management and Orchestration (SMO), RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs), the 5G core network functions that directly interface with RAN nodes, Network Function Virtualization -Management & Orchestration (NFV-MANO) and the Software Defined Network (SDN) control as an external service.

VRANs are key enablers for improving energy efficiency for mobile networks' operation [2]. Their deployments flexibility, exemplified in [3], ensures the fulfilment of stringent requirements for heterogeneous scenarios of next-generation networks [4]. Figure 1 presents the essential functionalities that comprise the vision of this article of a VRAN. It is assumed that rApp traffic forecast informs xApp Machine Learning (ML) optimization for instance compute scheduling [5]. The extension of the optimization proposed will also adapt the transport infrastructure using Software Defined Networks (SDN) controller [6], and the deployment of O-RAN [7] identified units Central Unit (CU), Distributed Unit (DU) and Radio Unit (RU), deployed per slice as VNFs. Figure 2 presents the flowchart of the algorithm for optimizing a slice's link. The flowchart operates as a loop until achieving an optimal state for each slice across all adjustable links. The colour scheme of the blocks corresponds to the Fig 1 components, e.g. the actions related to VNFs control are implemented with Network Function Virtualization -Management & Orchestration (NFV-MANO) with it also being used for informing the decisions. The decision process prioritizes centralization, where the co-located processing enables the execution of interference mitigation techniques e.g. Coordinated Multipoint (CoMP). Deploying a separate unit will lead to processing inefficiencies; therefore, prioritizing changes that most significantly improve transport efficiency is essential. To balance these two aspects, RU should be deployed using Open Fronthaul, as it will provide the best trade-off from a centralized architecture. In the cases where processing is necessary within the xhaul with CUs/DUs, where further centralization is not possible, the

Figure 2: Dynamic Functional Split Orchestration Algorithms' Flowchart of decisions to adapt a link per slice.

bandwidth requirements should be assured according to a slice's priority. Prompting the optimization of conflicting slices' to free necessary resources. Another consideration is latency per slice, to this end three actions are considered: the split of user and control planes, the deployment of the User Plane Function (UPF) closer to the user and finally the migration of the units of the slice to be optimized. The preferred medium of transport should be optical, here envisioned as a Passive Optical Network (PON) integrating Reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs). Nonetheless, control of the links will be done over metrics agnostic to the medium, enabling the usage of other mediums. The algorithm must be executed per interval of the forecast, falling in line with the development of such functionality as a rApp. However, the optimizations should be sent to xApps, so that any near real-time optimization is not done over an outdated network topology. Adjusting the split based on ML forecast requirements will minimize the considerable impact of altering the network topology for various scenarios [8]. This work sought a solution for the Dynamic Functional Split by integrating the O-RAN SMO framework, SDN control and NFV MANO. It did so by proposing an algorithm that would orchestrate the RAN for each link for every slice, mapping the different considerations to the logical blocks that would support the optimization.

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